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1. Abbreviations

CMR: compact membrane reactor

CO: confidential

D: deliverable

EIS: electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

SEM: scanning electron microscopy

2. Summary

This document outlines the work developed in Task 4.3, which aimed to evaluate the performance of the Compact Membrane Reactor (CMR) components developed in WP4 under single-fuel conditions. A schematic of the CMR components and the working principle is illustrated in Figure 1. This task focuses on the characterization of the manufactured full-cells, which consist of the half cells developed at FZJ together with the hydrogen (top) electrode developed at CSIC. The study includes structural characterization, including XRD and SEM and also, electrochemical characterization carried out under single-fuel conditions using hydrogen (H_2) and ammonia (NH_3). These results provide critical insights into the behavior and optimization of electrode materials for future integration into complete CMR systems.

Figure 1: Illustration of the CMR components and working principle.

3. H₂ electrodes and CMRs (or full cells) fabrication

3.1. Top electrode

The H₂ electrode was developed with a composition of 40% BaZr_{0.7}Ce_{0.2}Y_{0.1}O_{3-δ} (BZCY721) and 60% Ni by volume. Commercial BZCY721 powder (Cerpotech) was ball-milled for 72 hours. Then, the powder was mixed with NiO (Marion Technologies) and ball-milled for 24 hours. We adjusted the NiO percentage in order to achieve the desired percentage of Ni (after reduction).

The resulting electrode powders were sieved to 100 μm and mixed with terpineol (Sigma Aldrich) to produce an ink. Terpineol served as the vehicle, initially used in a 1:1 ratio with the powder. However, this formulation yielded electrode layers that were excessively thick. To improve layer consistency, the vehicle content was increased to a 1:1.5 powder-to-vehicle ratio.

For electrode adhesion, a sintering temperature of 1250 °C for 7 hours was initially applied, but the resulting layers failed the adhesion test. Subsequently, sintering at 1350 °C for 7 hours yielded good adhesion, establishing this as the optimum sintering condition. The fabrication procedure for the top electrode is illustrated in the schematic shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Scheme of the top electrode fabrication procedure.

3.2. Full cells development

The optimized H₂ electrode powders were screen-printed onto the BaZr_{0.7}Ce_{0.2}Y_{0.1}O₃ electrolyte of half-cells supported on NiO-SrZr_{0.5}Ce_{0.4}Y_{0.1}O₃ fabricated at FZJ. Figure 3 shows representative SEM images of the prepared full cells with the optimized electrode. The electrolyte showed a thickness of ~10 μm, the H₂ electrode of ~20 μm and the support of ~400 μm. The H₂ electrode (top electrode) developed and optimized at CSIC showed good adhesion and porosity around 25-30%, with a uniform particle size distribution around 0.5-1 μm and no agglomeration.

Figure 3. Scheme of the full cells and SEM images of the top electrode and the full cells developed in this work.

Figure 4 shows the XRD patterns of the electrode BZCY721-Ni after the reduction at 750 °C in 20% H₂. Both BZCY and Ni phases can be observed, with no secondary phases detected.

Figure 4. XRD patterns of the BZCY721-Ni electrode after the reduction at 750 °C in 20% H₂.

4. Electrochemical characterization in symmetrical atmosphere

4.1. Electrochemical characterization results in H₂

The electrochemical performance of the developed full cells was evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using the BZCY721-Ni/BZCY721/SCZY541-Ni cells by feeding the same atmosphere into both chambers, here referred to as symmetrical atmosphere testing evaluation. For this purpose, the quartz reactor shown in Figure 5 was used. An alumina multibore with current collectors of Pt and a thermocouple was placed inside both chambers, which is also used to feed the gas.

Figure 5. Scheme of the electrochemical reactor setup used for symmetrical cells testing.

The reactor setup presented in Figure 6 was employed for the electrochemical studies. It is equipped with different mass flow controllers to feed several gases to the unit: ammonia, hydrogen, nitrogen, helium, argon and different gas cylinders; enabling it to operate under different conditions. The gases are mixed and fed to a quartz reactor where the temperature is controlled in the range of 25-1000 °C, at atmospheric pressure. The gas inlet can be humidified through the use of an evaporator.

Figure 6. High-temperature reactor setup used for electrochemical and catalytic characterization.

The first test was performed in humidified hydrogen (20% H₂ in Ar, 3% H₂O) in a temperature range from 700 to 500 °C. The impedance spectra measured under different conditions were fitted by using the electrical equivalent circuit shown in the inset of Figure 7(b). The polarization resistance of the electrodes is calculated by summing the two polarization resistance contributions ($R_P = R_{MF} + R_{HF}$), where MF and HF refer to the medium and high frequency resistances, respectively.

Figure 7 (b) and (c) shows the impedance spectra (Nyquist and Bode) of the cell, where two distinct contributions can be identified: (i) MF contribution with associated frequencies of 1 to 100 Hz and capacitances between 10⁻³ and 10⁻⁴ F/cm²; and (ii) HF contribution with associated frequencies above 1 kHz and capacitances between 10⁻⁵ and 10⁻⁷ F/cm². The MF contributions are typically associated with elemental reactions occurring at the electrode surface, such as the adsorption and dissociation of gas molecules, which are part of the surface exchange kinetics. In contrast, the HF contribution is attributed to proton and electronic losses occurring at the interfaces between the electrode and the electrolyte or the electrode and the current collector. As can be observed, the limiting step of the electrode appears at high frequencies.

However, as shown in Figure 7(a), the limiting step of the overall reaction occurs in the electrolyte, as the ohmic resistance is greater than the polarization resistance. This behavior changes with temperature; as the temperature increases, the polarization resistance also increases and becomes higher than the ohmic resistance at 500 °C.

Figure 7. (a) Polarization and ohmic resistance contributions, (b) Bode and (c) Nyquist plots (ohmic resistances subtracted) measured by EIS in wet 20% H₂ from 500 to 700 °C.

4.2. Electrochemical characterization results in NH₃

Also, the full cell was electrochemically evaluated in wet ammonia (50% NH₃ + 50% Ar) at 700 °C. Figure 8 shows the impedance data acquired during 15 hours, revealing severe cell degradation from 1.83 to 3.98 Ω·cm² for the ohmic resistance. A high-frequency contribution can be distinguished, with this being the limiting step, mostly attributed to losses in the electronic pathway, which might indicate nickel reoxidation with time.

Figure 8. Nyquist and Bode plots of the full cell measured by EIS in wet 50% NH₃ at 700 °C.

Additionally, the cell was measured in dry ammonia (50% NH₃ + 50% Ar) (Figure 9) at 700 °C. The cell experienced degradation over the 5-hour test. In the Bode plot can be observed that the limiting resistance of the process occurs in the electrolyte, since the ohmic resistance is higher than the polarization resistance. If the ohmic resistance is compared with Figure 8, it can be observed that the ohmic resistance suffers less degradation, increasing from 1.33 to 1.38 Ω·cm² instead of from 1.83 to 2.83 Ω·cm² during the first 5 hours of testing.

Figure 9. Nyquist and Bode plots of the full cell measured by EIS in dry 50% NH₃ at 700 °C.

It was initially suspected that the degradation could be due to reoxidation of Ni under ammonia-only conditions. For this reason, the cell was evaluated at 700 °C with H₂ co-feeding under both wet and dry conditions using a mixture of 40% NH₃ + 18% H₂ + 42% Ar, as shown in Figure 10 (a) and (b), respectively. The performance and stability of the cell is higher under these conditions. These enhanced properties can be related to the presence of humidified H₂.

Effective reduction treatment prior to the NH_3 cracking reaction, along with sufficient contact time, is essential for achieving high CMR performance. In the current setup, the contact time between NH_3 and the electrodes was too short, limiting the extent of NH_3 cracking. This limitation can also be attributed to the small electrode area and the high gas flow rates. Additionally, low H_2 concentrations at the electrodes may lead to Ni reoxidation, further reducing cell performance. Therefore, optimizing operational conditions and electrode design is critical. Moreover, continued development of stable alternative electrode materials compatible with humidified NH_3 offers a promising route for enhancing long-term cell durability.

Figure 10. Nyquist and Bode plots of the full cell measured by EIS in (a) wet and (b) dry 40% NH_3 -18% H_2 at 700 °C.

4.3. Structural post-mortem characterization

Figure 11 shows the cross-sectional SEM images and XRD patterns of the developed full cells and H_2 electrodes after the electrochemical testing under the different atmosphere conditions used:

- (a) Full cell reduced at 750 °C in 20% H_2 and 80% Ar.
- (b) Full cell measured at 700 °C in wet 40% NH_3 , 18% H_2 and 42% Ar.
- (c) Full cell measured at 700 °C in dry 50% NH_3 and 50% Ar.

In cases (a) and (b), both electrodes exhibit higher porosity and improved dispersion, with XRD patterns confirming the presence of Ni and BZCY phases. In contrast, case (c) shows significantly reduced porosity, indicative of insufficient reduction, and the XRD results reveal the presence of the NiO phase. These findings highlight that effective pre-reduction or H_2 co-feeding during the ammonia reaction is essential to maintain adequate electronic conductivity and achieve optimal performance, particularly when small electrode areas and low residence times are used.

Figure 11. SEM cross-sectional images and XRD patterns of the full cells after (a) reduction in 20% H₂ at 750 °C, and after the electrochemical tests performed at 700 °C in (b) wet 40% NH₃-18% H₂ and (c) dry 50% NH₃.

5. Conclusions

The development of microstructurally optimized H₂ electrodes has proven essential for enhancing the performance and stability of the full cells operating in ammonia-containing environments. These optimized electrodes provide a foundation for identifying suitable testing conditions under NH₃ atmospheres and will contribute significantly to achieving high CMR efficiencies.

However, the study also reveals that limited contact time between NH₃ and the electrodes, due to small electrode area and high gas flow rates (low residence time), hinders the ammonia cracking reaction. Additionally, low hydrogen concentrations at the electrodes can result in Ni reoxidation, leading to a decline in cell performance. Therefore, either a proper reduction treatment before NH₃ exposure or sufficient contact time is critical to achieving optimal performance.

Finally, the ongoing development of electrode materials with improved stability under wet conditions presents a valuable opportunity for advancing the long-term durability and operational reliability of ammonia-fed CMR systems.